

Automatic identification of potential outliers in large data bases of time series based on autoencoders. Application to dam monitoring data

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ABSTRACT

The development of machine learning techniques has promoted their application in various fields of engineering, including hydraulics and hydrology. Models of this type have been shown to be capable of generating highly accurate and useful predictions in several areas. However, many of the applications are limited to cases in which the available information is abundant and of good quality. Less attention has been paid to situations – common in professional practice – in which the available data has issues such as periods without records, potentially erroneous values or heterogeneous reading frequency. These problems are even more relevant when dealing with relatively large databases, when visual exploration of each of the series is unfeasible. We present the results of the application of autoencoder neural networks for the automatic filtering of potentially anomalous values from a dam monitoring database with several hundred variables.

1. Introduction

Machine learning (ML) based predictive models are applied with increasing frequency in the field of hydraulic and hydrological engineering, from floods (López-Chacón *et al.*, 2023) to dam response (Mata, 2011, Salazar, 2017) or the discharge capacity of hydraulic structures (Salazar and Crookston, 2019). Many published works show improved performance as compared to conventional methods in terms of speed of calculation, accuracy or ability to capture non-linear effects or interactions. Since these models rely exclusively on data, their usefulness is highly conditioned by the quality and variety of the data available. The vast majority of application examples refer to cases in which the data series are adequate, sufficiently long and of good quality. However, preprocessing methods have been much less studied, which limits the application of these techniques in situations of scarcity or poor quality of data, which frequently occur in practice. This preliminary phase is particularly important during the process of digitizing databases of historical series, as is the case of monitoring systems of many dams: the installation of automatic systems allows increasing the reading frequency and the size of the database, but it requires unifying the previous records, taken manually, with the new ones. Frequently, these databases are made up of dozens or even hundreds of series, which makes detailed visual inspection of each of them inefficient or even unfeasible. In this communication, we present the results of the application of autoencoders, a method based on neural networks, to automatically detect errors in dam monitoring databases in which exploratory analysis is not feasible due to the large number of existing data series.

2. Methodology

2.1. Autoencoders

Autoencoders are a type of neural networks whose initial objective is the encoding of the information provided by a large number of sensors to a lower-dimensional latent space, for subsequent reconstruction of the original signal. This technique has been used to detect anomalies in systems such as wind turbines (Feijóo *et al.*, 2021): the autoencoder is trained with normal operating data, so that when it is presented with anomalous measurements, the reconstruction fails, allowing a possible deviation to be identified. Following a similar idea,

we trained an autoencoder with all the variables from a dam monitoring database and then applied it to the reconstruction of the original data. The mean absolute error (MAE) between the output of the autoencoder and the original record is computed, which can be considered an abnormality index. Subsequently, all records can be sorted based on their MAE, so that the dam owner can prioritize those with the highest probability of being reading errors or specific anomalies.

2.2. Case study

This technique has been applied to monitoring data from a dam, whose records cover a period of 30 years, with 1,870 variables and 15,721 rows. The procedure for detecting outliers includes the following steps: a) filtering of series with physical meaning, after which 429 variables are kept; b) training of an autoencoder and application to the reconstruction of the original data; c) calculation of the reconstruction MAE for each observation of each series; d) filtering of variables with some observation with MAE greater than a threshold; e) visual review of potentially anomalous data and correction, if applicable.

3. Results

Figure 1 shows the plot of the potentially anomalous values. Only variables that have some record with reconstruction MAE above the threshold appear. The same figure shows, as an example, two of the potential outliers identified. The final decision on whether it is a reading error or an anomalous situation must be made by an expert, considering the nature of the sensor and the life history of the dam, but the tool makes that task approachable, thanks to automatic preliminary filtering. We are currently evaluating the ability of other ML-based methods for this purpose, including DBSCAN and Local Outlier Factor (Ferreira *et al.*, 2023). In addition, we are exploring options to help understanding the cause of the anomalous vales, such as cluster analysis.

Fig. 1. Left: Potential outliers identified (the original plot is interactive). Right: Examples of identified values (highlighted in red) in two of the series.

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